

Rolling Bearing Fault Detection using Deep Learning Model: Intelligent Manufacturing Industry 4.0 / 5.0

Ahmad Sarwar

*School of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering,
Wuhan University of Technology, China*

Dua Sarwar

School of Information Technology, Punjab University, Pakistan

Muhammad Usman Shams

*Institute of Computer & Software Engineering,
Khawaja Fareed University of Engineering and Information Technology, Pakistan*

Muhammad Islam

*Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology,
Punjab Tianjin University of Technology, Pakistan*

Muhammad Jahanzaib Afzal

*Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology,
Punjab Tianjin University of Technology, Pakistan*

Amsh Bin Yasir

*Department of Computer Science,
National College of Business Administration & Economic, Pakistan*

Abstract

This paper proposes a new problem diagnosis method for smart and heavy manufacturing bearings. Instead of feature extraction, the suggested method processes defect signals with a convolutional neural network (CNN). It solves the problems of weak fault signals and high background noise, which lower diagnostic accuracy. The approach also quantifies diagnostic results, making fault severity assessment easier. To eliminate manual knowledge in existing methods, a one-dimensional convolutional deep neural network model is constructed to intelligently derive defect characteristics from intelligent manufacturing industry 4.0 bearing vibration data. The accuracy of this method was compared to wavelet threshold denoising and ensemble empirical mode decomposition data denoising for diagnostic recognition. This technology has engineering merit in identifying smart industry 4.0/5.0 bearing concerns.

Keywords: bearing fault diagnosis, CNN, end-to-end, industry 4.0/5.0.

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Introduction

Industry 4.0/5.0 and rapid science and technology advancement are making mechanical equipment larger and more precise (Rani, et al., 2024; Shoukat, et al., 2022; Justus, & Kanagachidambaresan, 2024; Maurya, et al., 2024). Humans have raised mechanical equipment operating safety, stability, and intelligence standards. The condition of rolling bearings is essential to the normal process of mechanical equipment because they connect and transmit power (Mu, & Antwi-Afari, 2024). Bearings are vital for large-scale rotating machinery in many sectors. These bearings are prone to failure and endure heavy external loads and hard operating conditions, compromising equipment safety and causing significant economic losses (Krot, Korennoi, & Zimroz, 2020; Abdul Jawwad, et al., 2023). Thus, bearing fault diagnosis research is crucial. Due to the rapid advancement of electrical technology, there are now several techniques available for detecting issues with rolling bearings. Typical diagnostic methods include oil analysis, temperature measurement, vibration analysis, driving voltage analysis, and driving current analysis.

The vibration signal diagnostic approach has gained noteworthy attention in the field of industry 4.0 bearing failure detection due to its real-time and efficient feedback, positive application effects, cost-effectiveness, and ease of signal collection (Liu, 2023; Cui, et al., 2020). This approach involves the placement of acceleration sensors on the bearing base or equipment casing to collect vibration signals of the equipment while it is in operation. Subsequently, it is possible to extract features from these signals in order to accomplish fault differentiation for various categories of bearings. The usual technique to defect diagnostics in rolling bearings involves the crucial task of reconstructing and deconstructing vibration signals. Bearing vibration signals may be analyzed using several signal analysis techniques, including as wavelet transform, local mean decomposition, empirical mode decomposition, and short-time Fourier transform. Experts determine the kind and position of faults by closely examining reconstructed signals, drawing heavily on their empirical expertise.

Currently, there is a predominant emphasis in the study on fault diagnoses for industry 4.0 manufacturing bearings on the manual extraction of fault characteristics. Yu et al., (2006) divided the vibration signal using EMD, calculated the energy entropy of the decomposed signals of different components, and used it as a feature vector. They combined it with artificial neural networks to distinguish faults in the inner and outer rings of bearings. Li et al., (2010) first separate the vibration signal into several components through VMD decomposition, and screened the components through indicators such as envelope entropy, correlation coefficient, etc. Secondly, extract features such as time-domain, frequency-domain, and energy entropy from the filtered components and form feature vectors. Then input the feature vectors into the support vector machine (SVM) enhanced by the sparrow search algorithm to achieve diagnosis of different fault samples. After a series of decomposition and recombination processes on the original vibration signal, it is essential to extract features from the signal with signal fault characteristics and complete fault type recognition.

Wang et al., (2021) conducted Hilbert envelope spectrum analysis on one-dimensional time-series bearing signals and combined the obtained envelope spectrum with deep confidence networks to achieve diagnosis of different types of bearing faults. Zhao et al., (2021) transformed one-dimensional time-series signals into two-dimensional grayscale feature maps and combined them with CNN to extract bearing fault features, achieving fault diagnosis of bearings. Zhang et al., (2020) used Fourier transform to convert signals into two-dimensional images, and used the SELU function as a CNN activation function to complete the identification of equipment fault types. Yuxiang et al., (2023) improved the residual network ResNet18 and transformed the signal into a two-dimensional time-frequency map through STFT, greatly enhancing the diagnostic accuracy of

the model. Guo et al., (2023) proposed a diagnostic method based on bidirectional long short-term memory network for fault diagnosis in small sample situations. By integrating empirical mode decomposition and Fourier transform to construct a feature matrix, combined with the proposed network, fault diagnosis under small sample conditions was achieved. Among the various detection methods mentioned above, vibration analysis method has become the most widely used method in the field of fault diagnosis due to its advantages of simple signal acquisition, low cost, strong timeliness, and reliable diagnostic results. As shown in Figure 1, the bearing fault diagnosis method based on vibration signals can be mainly divided into four parts, namely vibration signal acquisition, signal processing, feature extraction, and fault recognition.

Figure 1. Fault Diagnosis Process for Rolling Bearings

The signal processing and fault recognition parts are of utmost importance in achieving bearing fault diagnosis, and have a significant impact on the accuracy and speed of diagnostic results. However, the fault information of smart manufacturing industries bearings is weak, it is difficult to extract stable characteristic spectral lines in the frequency domain, and there is a gap between the theoretical value and the real value of the bearing fault characteristic frequency, which is easy to miss fault information, resulting in low accuracy of diagnostic results. Based on the aforementioned, this research makes several unique contributions.

- The ability of CNN to adaptively extract signal features was used to realize the end-to-end fault feature extraction of bearings.
- Then, the confusion matrix was used to obtain the accuracy and recall of the diagnostic results, and the quantitative evaluation of the diagnostic results was realized.

Preliminary

The convolutional layer applies a convolution operation on the input data using the convolution kernel in order to extract the characteristics of the input layer. The method for calculating the convolution operation is as follows:

$$Y^t = f(\sum_i^n K^t X_i^{t-1} + O^t) \tag{1}$$

where, X_i^{t-1} is the input feature parameter of layer t , and Y^t is the feature parameter of layer t after convolution. The K^t is the convolution kernel, O^t is the convolution kernel offset, and f is

the activation function. The activation function presents nonlinear factors into the neural network to improve the fitting ability of the network and realize the fitting of complex functions (Wu, et al., 2023). As a commonly used activation function of CNNs, the ReLU (rectified linear unit) activation function can solve the problem of backpropagation gradient disappearance in gradient descent algorithms and accelerate the convergence of neural networks. The function analysis of the ReLU activation function is as follows:

$$f(Y) = \begin{cases} 0, & X < 0 \\ X, & X \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The pooling operation of the pooling layer can be divided into maximum pooling and average pooling, the maximum pooling is to extract the maximum value of adjacent elements in step size with the pooling kernel to achieve variable reduction of features, and the average pooling is to extract the average value of each element to simplify the structure of the model (Yuan, et al., 2023). The fully connected layer flattens the feature matrix output by the pooling layer and converts it into a one-dimensional vector. Finally, the classifier is used to classify the previously extracted signal features. The basic structure of a CNN is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Basic Structure of Convolutional Neural Network

It can be seen in Figure 2, input layer receives the raw data, such as vibration signals or images, associated with the bearings. Convolutional layers: These layers are responsible for extracting features from the input data. Convolutional layers use filters (or kernels) to sliding over the input and produce feature maps. The number and size of filters, as well as the number of convolutional layers, can vary depending on the complexity of the task. Pooling layers down-sample the feature maps to reduce the spatial dimensions and capture invariant features. Common pooling operations include max pooling or average pooling. Fully-connected layers connect all the features and map them to the desired output, such as fault classes or fault severity.

Experimental Verification and Analysis

Dataset

In order to verify the effectiveness of the method proposed in this paper, it is necessary to carry out a fault diagnosis experiment of smart manufacturing industry bearings to obtain the bearing vibration signal. The bearing fault diagnosis test bench used in this experiment is shown in Figure 3, including a motor, a coupling, a bearing housing, a loading device, and a vibration sensor is installed on the outside of the bearing housing.

Figure 3. Bearing Fault Diagnosis Test Bench

As a result of their similar basic structure and size, the NU205EM and N205M cylindrical roller bearings were chosen as the subjects of this study. During the bearing fault diagnosis experiment, the LC16A01 vibration acceleration sensor was used to collect the bearing vibration signal, with a sampling frequency of 25600Hz. According to the discrimination criteria for low-speed and heavy-duty working conditions of bearings, it is necessary to apply a radial load exceeding 4950N to the tested bearing, while maintaining the spindle speed below 600r/min, to ensure that the bearing is always in a low-speed and heavy-duty working state during the experimental data collection process.

Consequently, this paper compiles vibration data pertaining to bearings in four distinct states, namely outer ring fault, inner ring fault, rolling element fault, and normal. The experimental conditions encompassed spindle speeds of 43.2r/min, 86.4r/min, and 129.6r/min, while subjecting the bearings to a radial load of 5000N. In order to replicate the malfunctioning condition of bearings, several bearings of identical design were placed on the outer ring, inner ring, and rolling element. Additionally, grooves with a cross-sectional dimension of 0.1mm x 0.1mm were created.

The bearing vibration signal is partitioned into data sets, and the fault diagnosis data set identifies four bearing states: normal state, outer ring fault, inner ring fault, and rolling element fault. Each fault state consists of 250 data samples, with each data sample containing 8192 points, resulting in a total of 1000 data samples. The vibration data for various working conditions are categorized into four distinct categories. The training set and the test set are divided in a ratio of 1:1. As a result, three datasets of bearing vibrations, one for low-speed and one for heavy-load situations, are obtained. The sample structure of these datasets is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Structure of the Dataset

Number	Status	Speed (r/min)	Label	Training set	Test set
1	Rolling element fault	43.2	0	200	50
2	Inner ring fault	43.2	1	200	50
3	Outer ring fault	43.2	2	200	50
4	Normal	43.2	3	200	50
5	Rolling element fault	86.4	0	200	50
6	Inner ring fault	86.4	1	200	50
7	Outer ring fault	86.4	2	200	50
8	Normal	86.4	3	200	50
9	Rolling element fault	129.6	0	200	50
10	Inner ring fault	129.6	1	200	50
11	Outer ring fault	129.6	2	200	50
12	Normal	129.6	3	200	50

Results and Analysis

The training and testing sets were input into the network model established in this article. The initial iteration batch size of the neural network was 8. After 100 iterations, the fault diagnosis accuracy of the three working condition datasets, 43.2r/min, 86.4r/min, and 129.6r/min, were obtained, which were 87%, 98.5%, and 99%, respectively. Taking the accuracy (Acc) curve and loss value (Loss) curve of the bearing fault diagnosis obtained under the operating condition of 86.4r/min as an example, the specific images are shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. Fault Diagnosis Accuracy curve

Figure 5. Fault Diagnosis Loss Value Curve

Based on the diagnostic accuracy curve and loss value curve, the model achieves an accuracy of over 99% on the training set after 60 iterations, and a diagnostic accuracy curve of over 90% on the test set. The loss value curves of both the training and test sets exhibit a convergence towards zero, suggesting that the model possesses the capability to successfully perform fault diagnosis tasks. In order to reflect the superiority of this paper, the deep neural network diagnostic model after data preprocessing is compared with the references (Sandoval, et al., 2020; Ji, et al., 2021).

According to literature (Sandoval, et al., 2020), wavelet thresholding denoising is applied to the raw data of bearings: a 4th order multi-Bessie wavelet (db4 wavelet) is selected as the wavelet basis function to perform wavelet decomposition on the original signal, obtain coefficients at various scales, and then filter the signal according to the adaptive denoising threshold obtained. Subsequently, after wavelet reconstruction, the denoised bearing vibration signal is obtained. According to Ji, et al., (2021), perform ensemble empirical mode decomposition and signal reconstruction on the original bearing data: first, perform ensemble empirical mode decomposition on the vibration data, and calculate the cross-correlation coefficients between each intrinsic mode function (IMF) component and the original signal. By removing weakly correlated IMF components and reconstructing the remaining components, noise reduction processing of vibration data is achieved. The optimal diagnostic result was obtained through parameter adjustment, and the final fault diagnosis result is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of Fault Diagnosis Results of Bearings

Diagnostic accuracy of different data processing methods	Bearing speed (r/min)		
	43.2	86.4	129.6
Sandoval, et al., 2020	76 %	92 %	93 %
Ji, et al., 2021	83.5 %	98 %	98.5 %
Proposed work	87 %	98.5 %	99 %

The data presented in Table 2 shows that the end-to-end method exhibits superior diagnostic accuracy compared to the other two control methods across the three speed conditions chosen for the experiment. Furthermore, it is observed that as the speed decreases, the disparity between the accuracy of the end-to-end diagnostic method and the manual data processing method increases.

Analyze the reasons: 1) The fault information of bearings has the characteristics of low frequency and low signal-to-noise ratio. Due to the low speed of bearings, the bearing vibration signal frequency is low and the fault signal is weak, and the heavy-load condition will bring strong background noise, so that the signal-to-noise ratio of the collected bearing vibration signal is low, and the fault feature extraction is difficult. 2) Wavelet threshold noise reduction is essentially an inner product transformation. Wavelet threshold noise reduction: When dealing with low-frequency signals, the noise reduction threshold is large, and the wavelet coefficient is easy to be mistaken for noise, resulting in false rejection. EEMD decomposition: When dealing with low-frequency signals, the IMF components are not much different and are easy to aliasing, resulting in no obvious noise reduction effect. 3) By employing the maximum pooling operation in the pooling layer to compress the signal's features, the CNN is capable of mapping the characteristics of the gathered data. This enables the network to perform adaptive feature extraction and feature enhancement on the signal, thereby enhancing the accuracy of fault diagnosis for bearings.

Quantitative Evaluation

The confusion matrix is drawn to visually express the fault diagnosis results. Taking the data of 86.4 r/min as an example, the confusion matrix of the diagnostic results of the method used in this paper is shown in Figure 6.

The model diagnosis result is represented on the horizontal axis, while the actual fault state of the bearing is represented on the longitudinal axis. The number on the diagonal indicates the diagnostic accuracy, with a darker color on the diagonal indicating more accuracy in diagnosis. The confusion matrix is used to compute the accuracy, precision, and recall of the model. The results of these calculations are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

The calculation results demonstrate that the end-to-end fault diagnosis method employed in this study outperforms the methods described in Literatures Sandoval, et al., (2020) and Ji, et al., (2021). Specifically, the diagnostic accuracy and recall rate for detecting outer ring faults reach 100%, with only a few misclassifications observed for bearings in other fault states. This performance surpasses the diagnosis outcomes achieved through data processing in Literatures 30 and 31. These findings confirm that the proposed method effectively diagnoses bearing faults.

Figure 6. Diagnostic Results of this Method Under the Condition of 86.4 r/min

Table 3. Evaluation Index of Proposed Work Under Working Condition of 86.4 r/min in (%)

Evaluation index	Rolling element	Inner ring	Outer ring	Normal
Accuracy ACC	98.9			
Precision PPV	100	97	99	100
Recall rate TPR	99	100	100	98

Table 4. Evaluation Index of 86.4r/min Working Condition Literature 31 in (%)

Evaluation index	Rolling element	Inner ring	Outer ring	Normal
Accuracy ACC	98			
Precision PPV	98.04	100	100	94.23
Recall rate TPR	100	96	98	98

Conclusion

This study presents an end-to-end fault diagnosis method based on a convolutional neural network as a solution to the challenges of difficult fault feature extraction, low diagnostic accuracy, and difficult quantitative evaluation of diagnostic results for smart-manufacturing industry bearings. The method's efficacy in diagnosing such bearings is validated through experiments involving low-speed heavy-load bearing fault diagnosis, thereby establishing its favorable diagnostic impact. The proposed method is very good at finding faults in both low-speed and heavy-load bearings. In addition, the method that is proposed in this paper has the capability to diagnose the fault of bearings, reduce the dependence on the experience of data processing experts, realize the fault diagnosis of low-speed and heavy-duty bearings, improve the accuracy of diagnosis, and finish the quantitative evaluation of the results of the diagnosis. In the future work, a novel hybrid deep learning model, as well as digital twin technique will be employed to monitor and diagnose the condition of the bearings.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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